

RESPECCT

REspiratory syncytial virus and S. pnEumoniae Challenge Coinfection sTudy

Date

Oxford Vaccine Group

Participant's name: _____

Participant's initials: _____

Participant screening number: _____

Consent Form

Please initial the box if you agree with each statement. Then, print and sign and date below.

Section 1: Study Procedures	
I have read and understood the participant information sheet version __ dated __/__/____/____ for the above study. I confirm that the study procedures and information have been explained to me. I have been able to consider the information, had the opportunity to ask questions and I am satisfied with the answers and explanations provided.	
I have spoken with Dr/Nurse _____ -	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw without giving any reason and without affecting my medical care or legal rights.	
I have received detailed information about the treatment schedule and potential side effects.	
I agree to be randomised to receive RSV and Spn challenge and I am aware of the risks and side effects associated with the challenge.	
I agree that the research team may share, use and store my personal information as described in this information leaflet.	
I will bring the 24-hour contact reply slip to the first study visit, signed by my 24-hour contact. I agree that the study team may contact this person if I cannot be contacted during the study	
Section 2: Personal Information	
I understand that relevant sections of my medical notes and data collected during the study including identifiable information may be looked at by individuals from the Oxford Vaccine Group, The University of Oxford (Sponsor), from regulatory authorities or monitors, and authorised representatives appointed by the	

Participant's number _____

Sponsor, where it is relevant to my taking part in this research. I give permission for these people to access my records.					
I agree to my General Practitioner (GP) being informed of my participation in this study.					
I agree that my GP can provide the research team with information regarding my medical and vaccination history and study staff can access my NHS medical records either via my GP or electronic patient records system or and equivalent NHS database.					
I agree to provide my bank account details including my account name, sort code and account number for reimbursement purposes. I understand that my bank details will be stored electronically as described in the information booklet. I understand that my personal information will be shared to the extent required to process or verify eligibility of payments as described in the information booklet.					
I understand TOPS is the Health Research Authority database that aims to prevent healthy volunteers from taking part in too many studies. I understand that only staff at Oxford Vaccine Group and other research units can use the database and the study team may call other units, or the study team may be called, to check volunteer details. I agree to my National Insurance (if UK citizen) or Passport number being used to register me on TOPS. I understand that it will be stored electronically for the duration of the study.					
I understand that the Sponsor Data Management and IT Team will be able to view my email address. I understand it will be held securely on a server at the University of Oxford.					
Section 3: Research samples and Data					
I agree to donate blood, saliva, throat swab and nasal samples (washings, swabs, cells and nasosorption). I consider these samples a gift to the University of Oxford and understand I will not gain any direct personal or financial benefit from them.					
I agree to have blood tests as part of this trial, including testing for HIV, Hepatitis B and Hepatitis C					
I agree that my anonymised data and samples can be transferred outside of the UK for the purposes of this study, including being sent to Pfizer Inc. and other collaborators.					
I understand that some of my samples will be used to investigate genetic factors affecting infection and immunity and I understand that the results of these investigations will not have any implications for me personally.					
Section 4: Safety					
I agree to self-isolate as outlined in the participant information leaflet.					
Section 5: Other					
Females of childbearing potential only: I confirm that I am not planning to conceive, and I will use effective contraception during the study.					
If all the applicable sentences above are initialled, meaning "yes", then please continue:					
I voluntarily agree to take part in this study.					
Optional: Please Circle response and initial box					
I agree my contact details can be stored so that I may be contacted about ethically approved research studies for which I may be suitable in the future. I understand that agreeing to be contacted does not oblige me to participate in any further studies.	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Y</td> <td>N</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	Y	N		
Y	N				

Name of participant (print)

Signature

__/__/____
Date (dd-mon-YYYY)

Participant's number _____

Name of person taking consent

Signature

__/__/____
Date (dd-mon-YYYY)

Original – Investigator Site File, 1 Copy – Participant